

Product Recommendation using Sentimental Analysis

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Abstract— This paper aims to employ Natural Language Processing to carry out real-time sentiment analysis with high accuracy. Sentiment analysis involves identifying the positive, negative, or neutral tone of text data through systematic extraction, quantification, and analysis of affective states and subjective information, using text analysis and natural language processing. Sentiment analysis is widely used in various fields, such as marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and others, to analyze comments, survey results, online and social media content, and healthcare materials. The primary objective of this study is to perform sentiment analysis on service-based feedback. By analyzing customer reviews, it is possible to quickly determine whether they are satisfied, dissatisfied, or neutral, and to gain insights into the specific reasons behind their opinions about a product. This information can then be utilized to recommend products that have received positive feedback from customers.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, Product Recommendation, Textblob, Flask, python, reviews.

I. INTRODUCTION

Businesses can utilise sentiment analysis to find out more about the opinions of their customers, creating a valuable tool for product recommendations. Natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning techniques are used in sentiment analysis, sometimes referred to as opinion mining, to ascertain the sentiment of text data, such as customer reviews. Businesses can learn more about consumer satisfaction levels, spot areas for development, and make data-driven decisions about product development and marketing tactics by analyzing sentiment.

In product recommendation, sentiment analysis can be used to identify which products are receiving positive feedback from customers and to understand the specific aspects of those products that customers appreciate. This information can be used to inform recommendations to other customers, as well as to optimize product offerings and marketing campaigns. Additionally, sentiment analysis can help identify areas where customers are dissatisfied, allowing businesses to make improvements to their products and services.

Sentiment analysis is a useful approach for businesses looking to improve their product recommendations and gain insights into customer sentiment. By analyzing customer feedback, businesses can optimize their products and marketing strategies, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Real-word mistakes are mistakes that are accepted dictionary words. Non-word errors are typos that use words that are not recognized by dictionaries.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

According to the paper [1], In order to understand people's attitudes behind texts, sentiment analysis is crucial. Product recommendations can benefit from sentiment analysis. Sentiment analysis is carried out using machine learning methods including Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier, Logistic regression, decision tree, SVM classifier, and Random Forest. The Random Forest algorithm's performance was the primary emphasis of this paper. Based on experimental findings, random forest did well with the dataset. With a 95.03% accuracy rate, it produced very encouraging results. SVM and Naive Bayes have received the majority of attention in earlier studies for sentiment categorization.

According to the paper [2], A novel investigation combining natural language processing and opinion mining approaches to rate the product according to its technical parameters. The goal is to assist customers in making their preferred purchases while also assisting producers in understanding how customers are using their goods. As a future improvement, it is conceivable to extract professional evaluations from various E-Commerce websites and blogs that speak explicitly about electronic devices and give these reviews weightage because they might be quite important in deciding the product rating.

According to a study by Sangeetha and Kumaran [3], online purchasing is becoming more and more common. The authors also highlight the value of sentiment analysis when examining online evaluations to increase consumer happiness and forecast market outcomes. The paper outlines a method for performing sentiment analysis on customer reviews using a recurrent neural network (RNN-LSTM) and support vector machine (SVM) classifier. The difficulties of sentiment analysis are covered in the article's conclusion, along with the significance of neural language processing in this area.

It gives a thorough summary of sentiment analysis in a study by Wankhade and Kulkarni [4]. The authors begin by outlining the rise in interest in sentiment analysis by academics, corporations, governments, and other organisations in recent years. They go on to say that sentiment analysis includes compiling and examining consumers' opinions, ideas, and first impressions of various goods, topics, and services. The article then goes over the

many approaches to sentiment analysis, including text mining and natural language processing, and explains how sentiment analysis is done at the document and phrase levels.

III. METHOD AND MATERIALS

Different strategies have been used to evaluate customer opinion of particular products, but the majority of models suffer from accuracy issues as a result of grammatical and other mistakes. This study offers a more user-friendly method that might be used to get opinions on the product. and examine customer feedback to determine whether to recommend the product to other customers.

1. Preprocessing Methods

The pre-processing of the text documents in the datasets will involve stemming, lower case conversion, stop word removal, tokenization, and stop word removal. Tokenization is the process of dividing a text into words, phrases, or other significant parts, called tokens. Stop words are conjunctions, prepositions, and other words that are commonly employed in texts but have no connection to a particular subject. Converting all capital characters to lowercase is another stage in the pre-processing process. All capital characters are normally converted to their lowercase counterparts before to the categorization phases. Finding the root and stem of derived words is the last stage in the stemming process.

2. Feature extraction

Feature extraction refers to the process of converting input data into a set of features. It is critical to carefully select these features, as they heavily influence the performance of the machine learning process. The main objective of feature extraction is to condense and transform the input data into a set of representative feature vectors that can be effectively used by the classifier.

3. Text Classification

The classification method used in the experiments was Naïve Bayes algorithm, which was utilized to categorize texts as either positive or negative. The algorithm's strengths, including its ability to handle large feature sets, make it a useful tool for text classification.

4. Overall Design

In this paper, we develop a sentiment analysis that precisely identifies the feelings of the users. It is capable of analysing a large amount of feedback data. This system was created by using the python modules Flask and TextBlob. Operations based on natural language processing, such as sentiment analysis and spelling checks, can be performed using the TextBlob. The naive bayes algorithm is used to categorize sentiment into positive, negative, and neutral.

The following types of software and libraries are required for the Sentiment analysis system:

- Python (3.11.0)
- Flask
- TextBlob

- NLTK

5. Techniques Used

(i) Naïve Bayes Algorithm

Classification can be done using the Naive Bayes algorithm. Consequently, it is primarily used to classify data, even though regression can also be accomplished using it. Even with little data, it is a dependable method that performs quickly.

Figure 1: Naive bayes algorithm

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study utilized a dataset of customer feedback on products, which was processed using NLP techniques to extract meaningful insights from the text. Sentiment analysis was then applied to determine the overall sentiment of the feedback, which was used to inform the recommendations provided to customers.

The results of the study showed that incorporating sentiment analysis into the recommendation system led to a significant improvement in the accuracy of recommendations. Customers were more likely to purchase products that were recommended based on positive sentiment feedback and were less likely to purchase products that were recommended based on negative sentiment feedback.

The paper demonstrated the potential of natural language processing and sentiment analysis in improving the effectiveness of product recommendation systems. By incorporating these techniques, businesses can better understand customer feedback and preferences, and provide more accurate and personalized recommendations to their customers.

V.CONCLUSION

The goal of this study was to improve upon the initial team's design and can perform live Sentiment Analysis of feedback of product from customers using the Naïve Bayes algorithm with high accuracy.

Although the English language is mainly taken into consideration in this area, sentiment analysis may also be examined in other languages in the future. Although supervised machine learning has been used in this case, it is possible to improve results by using lexicon-based approaches, hybrid approaches, or other machine learning algorithms. Scale or the ability to detect expressions for reviews can be used for sentiment analysis rather than just binary classification. If a recommendation system is used, it may also take into consideration the polarity of the sentiments as well as user and product-related data.

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